

On estimating the optimal autoencoder model for denoising ECG using Akaike Information Criterion

Fars Samann^{1,2*} and Thomas Schanze¹

¹ Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT), Faculty of Life Science Engineering (LSE), Technische Hochschule Mittelhessen (THM) - University of Applied Sciences, Gießen, Germany

² Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Duhok, Duhok, Kurdistan Region-Iraq

* Corresponding author, email: Fars.samann@uod.ac

Abstract: Denoising biosignals, like ECG, via neural networks has shown an optimistic performance by encoding the original signal to a noise reduced signal, known as denoising autoencoder (DAE). The minimal requirements for DAE approach are one hidden layer of neurons and a learning rule. Here we show how-to find the optimal number of neurons receiving the input signal with respect to signal quality and computational burden by applying Akaike's information criterion (AIC). The novel approach is based on searching for the optimal DAE model which has the highest AIC's weight and optimal number of neurons.

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I. Introduction

Electrocardiogram (ECG) is a well-known tool for diagnosing cardiovascular disorders. Usually, ECG signal is contaminated with noise. Several methods of filtering have been proposed in the literature. A more recent approach of signal denoising is the use of neural network such as denoising autoencoder (DAE) [1-2]. The approach of DAE have demonstrated a significant improvement in denoising signals. However, the main problem in designing DAE model is to find the optimal number of hidden neurons. Many methods of estimating number of hidden neurons have been reported. Nevertheless, most of these methods were using statistical approaches and 'rules of thumb' to fix the number of hidden neurons [3-5]. These approaches may not give the optimal DAE model and require longer computational time. It is essential to find the optimal number of hidden neurons to obtain most efficient DAE model to overcome the overfitting or underfitting problem. The main scope of this study is to find the optimal DAE model for denoising ECG signals by considering Akaike's information criterion to select the DAE model with highest AIC's weight and optimal number of neurons.

II. Materials and methods

The proposed denoising autoencoder is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed denoising autoencoder.

II.I Denoising Autoencoder (DAE)

An autoencoder is a supervised neural network which is trained to replicate its input data as close as possible to its output. This approach is based on training the neural network with corrupted input signal to ignore the 'noise' by forcing it to learn the important features of the signal only via low-dimensional representation [1]. Where the corrupted signal \tilde{x} at the input layer is encoded to hidden representation z by considering nonlinear transformation f . Then, the hidden representation z is decoded back to the reconstructed signal \hat{x} as following [2]:

$$z = f(W\tilde{x} + b), \text{ where } f = \tanh(c\theta) \text{ and } c = 0.2 \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{x} = (\hat{W}z + \hat{b}) \quad (2)$$

where W, b and \hat{W}, \hat{b} are the weights and biases of the encoding and decoding process respectively. These weights and biases are optimized during the training process. Mean square error and adaptive moment estimation are used as loss function and optimizer for the compilation.

II.II Akaike's information criterion (AIC)

A collection of DAE models with different number of parameters, the AIC can be used to estimate the quality of the model with respect to other models [5].

$$AIC = n \ln(\text{mean}(\text{var}(x[i] - \hat{x}[i])) + 2K) \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of signal data points, and K is the number of hidden neurons, $x[i]$ and $\hat{x}[i]$ are the original and denoised ECG respectively. The best parameters of the DAE model can be estimated by the expected exponential likelihood as follow [5].

$$AIC_{weight} = \exp((AIC_{min} - AIC_j)/2) \quad (4)$$

Where AIC_j and AIC_{min} are the AIC value of j^{th} DAE model and minimum AIC value respectively. The optimal DAE model has the highest AIC's weight equal to 1 at specific number of neurons (see figure 2). However, figure 2 is clearly shown that the optimal DAE model for training and testing set are different. The aim of proposed method is to find the optimal number of neurons for both dataset.

Figure 2: AIC_{weight} curves for both training and testing set (noise level=45%) with respect to number of neurons

II.III Proposed algorithm

The proposed algorithm is developed using 'tensorflow' library for machine learning in Python 3.7 as follow:

1. Set the range of searching for optimal k : $5 < k < 30$
2. Calculating AIC_{weight} for DAE model in the search range for both training and testing dataset
3. The optimal k is the intersection point between $AIC_{weight_training}$ and $AIC_{weight_testing}$ curves (see figure 2)

III. Results and discussion

A PTB-XL database [6] is considered to provide clean ECG segments for training, validating, and testing datasets from 50 healthy patients. All ECG signals in the database are sampled with 500 Hz. From each patient, 10 ECG segments with a length of 95 samples are selected to create 300, 100 and 100 segments for the training, validation, and test groups, respectively. During training phase, a simulated Gaussian white noise of different levels 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% $\sigma(x)$ are added to generate a corrupted training and validating dataset respectively. A corrupted testing dataset is also generated for evaluating purposes. All ECG signals were normalized to limit the amplitude of the signals between -1 to 1. The performance of the DAE model with 1000 epochs is evaluated using the improvement in SNR and the AIC weight as a quantitative evaluation criteria.

Table 1: The estimated number of neurons k that required for training set, testing set and optimal value k

Noise level of testing set	Number of neurons k		
	Training set	Testing set	Optimal value k
15%	20	20	20
25%	20	18	19

35%	20	15	17
45%	20	14	16

The results presented in Table 1 and Figure 3 show that no significant increase in SNR is achieved after the estimated optimal value k for all noise levels. Therefore, it is possible to say that the proposed approach has selected the optimal DAE model with respect to the number of neurons and signal quality SNR_{imp} .

Figure 3: Optimal value k with respect to the SNR_{imp} curve at different noise levels of the testing dataset

IV. Conclusions

A novel approach for estimating the optimal DAE model for denoising ECG signal have been proposed in this work. The proposed approach is based on searching for the optimal number of hidden neurons using AIC weight with respect to signal quality SNR_{imp} . The performance of the proposed DAE model is evaluated using corrupted testing dataset with different white noise level. The results demonstrate that the optimal number of neurons for specific noise levels are estimated which gives the best improvement in SNR with minimum number of hidden neurons.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Special thanks to DAAD Research Grants Program to give me this opportunity to start my PhD under supervision of Prof. Dr. Thomas Schanze. We also want to thank Prof. Dr. Martin Fiebig for discussions.

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